

Direct Determination of Uranium in Seawater by Absorption Spectrophotometry

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Literature survey shows rare availability of spectrophotometric reagents with suitable Beer's law range¹ for the determination of uranium(VI). The proposed method has been applied to the determination of uranium in seawater.

Results and Discussion

Properties and characteristics of 1,3-bis-(salicylindeneamino)thiourea (SAT) are evaluated by the results of its elemental analysis and IR spectra (KBr) 1610 and 1540 (azomethine), 1260, 1020, 940 and 840 (C=S) and 3140–3000 cm^{-1} (hydrogen bonded OH and NH with water molecules). The method of Phillips and Merritt² was used to determine the pK_a value of the ligand (6.5). The pK_a value was evaluated as an arithmetic mean value obtained from measurements at four different wavelengths (275, 295, 322 and 350 nm).

The U^{VI} -SAT complex was found soluble in many organic solvents. As the complex showed a maximum absorbance in DMSO, this solvent was selected for the spectrophotometric studies. The absorption spectrum of uranium-SAT showed a maximum absorption at 386 nm, where the reagent showed least absorbance.

The effect of pH on the system was verified after taking a series of solutions of 3 ml of 1×10^{-3} M metal and 3 ml of 1×10^{-3} M ligand with 9.5 ml of DMSO. Then 3 ml of buffer solutions ranging from pH 0.5 to 9 were added and total volume of each was made up

to 25 ml with deionised water and the absorbance recorded at 386 nm. The maximum absorbance was obtained in pH 7.5. The addition of a three-fold excess of the reagent was sufficient for maximum constant absorbance.

The composition of the uranium-SAT complex was established by Job's method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method. In both the cases the uranium-to-ligand ratio was found to be 1:1.

The system obeyed Beer's law over the concentration range 0.1–130 ppm of UO_2^{2+} ions. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method were $6.4298 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.14 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

Various amounts of foreign ions were added to a fixed amount ($50 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and the recommended procedure for the spectrophotometric determination was followed. A maximum error of 2% in the absorbance reading was considered tolerable. Amongst the cations examined only tungsten interfered seriously. The reagent can be used with a reasonable selectivity of the method in the presence of associated foreign ions.

Application : In order to confirm the usefulness of the spectrophotometric method, it is applied to the determination of U^{VI} in natural sample corresponding to natural sample in seawater and the results are presented in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF SEAWATER

Sl no	Vol of sea-water taken	U content*	U content** µg/100 ml
1.	1000	62.0	6.2 (0.04)
2.	1500	100.5	6.7 (0.03)
3.	1700	101.5	5.8 (0.02)
4.	2000	130.0	6.5 (0.03)

*Average value of 5 measurements. **Figure in paranthesis indicates standard deviation.

Characterisation of the complex : In order to compare the solution studies with that of solid, uranium-SAT complex in solid state was isolated under identical condition and characterised by using spectral techniques.

Elemental analyses of solid complex (Found : C, 43.5; H, 3.54; N, 13.53; S, 7.6; U, 19.00. Calcd. for : C, 43.26; H, 3.66; N, 13.46; S, 7.69; U, 19.07%) reveal corresponding UO_2^{2+} to 1 : 3 composition against 1 : 1 in solution.

Ir spectral data reveal bonding sites of U^{VI} with SAT. The band at 1610 cm^{-1} shifted towards lower frequency ($1605, 1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), indicating participation of C=N group on coordination. The presence of 1590 cm^{-1} peak indicates the coordinated C=N, while 1605 cm^{-1} shows a weak interaction of C=N groups present freely in the other ligand molecules³. The bands due to ketone sulphur⁴ ($1020, 940, 840 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) did not suffer any change. The spectra shows non-participation of S atom on coordination. The absence of a band due to S-H stretching mode ($\sim 2570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggests that in solid state the reagent remains in thioketo form. Comparison of spectra before and after complexation reveals no change in OH frequency, confirming the non-participation of OH groups from reagent to metal through coordinate bond. The far-ir spectra shows two peaks at 570 (M-O) and $470 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ (M-N)}$.

The unaltered molar conductance value ($10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) recorded in DMSO at varied concentrations shows that the complex is non-ionic in nature. The magnetic susceptibility data (measured on V.S.M.) show diamagnetic behaviour of uranium-SAT complex as expected : ($-0.13,$

$-0.012, -0.011$ and 0.010) $\times 10^{-2}$ emu in field 4, 5, 6 and 7 kG respectively.

Experimental

All chemicals were of analytical reagent grade (E. Merck/B.D.H.).

To thiocarbohydrazide⁵ (50 mmol, 5.3 g) dissolved in 50% ethanol-water, was added glacial acetic acid (3 ml) followed by salicylaldehyde (0.1 mol, 10.6 g). The solution was warmed with constant stirring and the resulting yellow coloured solid was crystallised from 50% ethanol-acetone mixture, (85–90%), m.p. $191-192^\circ$. Stock solution of the ligand was prepared by dissolving $\text{SAT} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.314 g) in dimethyl sulphoxide (100 ml). Solutions of lower concentrations were obtained by dilution with DMSO.

A stock solution of uranyl acetate was prepared by dissolving uranyl acetate dihydrate (3.195 g) in minimum amount of double-distilled water, a few drops of acetic acid added and then made upto 250 ml. The solution was standardised⁶ gravimetrically before use.

Buffer solutions of various pH values were prepared using 0.2 M HCl, 1 M potassium chloride for pH 1–3, 2 M acetic acid, 1 M potassium hydroxide for pH 3.5–7 and 0.2 M ammonium chloride and 0.2 M aqueous ammonia for pH 8–12.

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a UVIDEK-340 spectrophotometer. An IITL digital pH meter with glass electrode was used for pH measurements.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the sample solution containing 0.1–130 ppm uranium(vi), were added buffer of pH 7.5 (3 ml), 1×10^{-4} M reagent solution (3 ml) and appropriate amount of DMSO. The contents were made up to 25 ml and absorbance was measured at 386 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of uranium in the sample solution was deduced from a standard calibration curve.

NOTE

Solid uranium-SAT complex : Uranyl acetate dihydrate (0.01 mol) dissolved in deionised water was mixed with an excess of the reagent solution and to it an appropriate amount of buffer solution (pH 7.5) was added. The light orange coloured solid that separated out, was washed with acetone-water mixture and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 .

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